

RADIOBLOCKS

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Industry Advisory Board meeting and report

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Executive summary

RADIOBLOCKS is a four-year project funded under the Horizon Europe program, with a budget of €9 million and thirty-three partners. It aims to significantly enhance European Research Infrastructures in radio astronomy by applying cutting-edge technology across the entire data chain, from the receiver to the final output. The project focuses on developing common technological building blocks applicable to various infrastructures, including novel detectors, digital receivers, data transport solutions, and advanced data processing tools.

RADIOBLOCKS seeks to drive innovation in radio astronomy and related fields, maximising its impact through industry engagement and dissemination to ensure the long-term sustainability of its results. The project embraces open science principles while addressing intellectual property rights.

To help direct the project's direction and improve industrial participation, RADIOBLOCKS has established an Industry Advisory Board (IAB) consisting of distinguished representatives from industry and related sectors. With the help of this board, the project aims to develop a targeted value proposition for industry partners, highlight success stories, and participate in key industry events.

1. Introduction

This document presents a comprehensive report on the meeting between the IAB and the RADIOBLOCKS executive team, held on 5 February 2025. The meeting was convened as a platform for exchanging insights, discussing progress, and charting future directions to maximise the project's impact on and its relevance to both the scientific community and the broader industrial landscape. The IAB will provide recommendations to help align the project's outputs with industry needs and maximise their potential for applications beyond the field of radio astronomy.

The members of the Industrial Advisory Board are:

- André Bos (S[&]T)¹
- Erik Kentie (SURF)²
- Miroslav Pantaleev (Beyond Gravity)³
- Ron Schram (Neways)⁴
- Adam Thompson (NVIDIA)⁵
- Andrey Baryshev (University of Groningen and RADIOBLOCKS representative)

¹ <https://www.stcorp.nl/>

² <https://www.surf.nl/>

³ <https://www.beyondgravity.com/en>

⁴ <https://newayselectronics.com/>

⁵ <https://www.nvidia.com/>

The other participants in the meeting were: Agnieszka Słowikowska, Giuseppe Cimò, Aukelien van den Poll, Arpad Szomoru, Ioanna Kazakou, Marjolein Verkouter (JIVE), John Romein, Roelien Attema-van Waas (ASTRON), Rob Beswick (UNIMAN), Carsten Kramer (IRAM), Stefan Heyminck (MPG), Pablo de Vicente (CNIG-OAN).

Specifically, the objectives of the IAB meeting were:

- To present the work done in the work packages, highlighting the participation of the current industrial partners and their impact on and involvement in the project,
- To obtain advice from the IAB on enhancing collaborations between academia and industry,
- To discuss ways to improve the dissemination of the project's results,
- To explore avenues for future cooperation with new industrial partners.

This report provides a summary of the presentations, discussions, and key recommendations that emerged from this meeting. In addition, it provides actionable advice to guide the RADIOBLOCKS project toward achieving its ambitious goals and realising its full potential.

2. Meeting report

2.1 Opening Remarks and Project Overview

Agnieszka Słowikowska (project coordinator) presented an overview of the RADIOBLOCKS project. The core concept of the project involves delivering building blocks across four major stages of signal and data flow that are common to all radio astronomical facilities. These stages correspond to the project's work packages:

- Novel detectors and components
- Digital receivers
- Data transport and correlation
- Data processing and post-processing.

A description of the governance structure of the project was given. The project coordinator also emphasised the importance of strong communication with the European Commission (EC), radio astronomical facilities, and industry partners.

2.2 Work Package Presentations

Each of the work package (WP) leaders presented their work, highlighting industrial partners' involvement and impact. The slides can be downloaded from the event page⁶.

⁶ <https://indico.astron.nl/event/406/>

2.2.1 WP1: Management

Giuseppe Cimò (project manager) described the managerial duties of the project. WP1 is responsible for supporting project activities, curating results, and ensuring accessibility. WP1 activities include maintaining the project website, developing communication tools and promotional materials, managing repositories, supporting Executive Team and General Assembly meetings, and developing and executing a dissemination plan.

Cimò emphasised the benefits for industries engaging with RADIOBLOCKS, including collaboration opportunities and access to a network of world-class research institutes.

2.2.2 WP2: Novel Detectors and Components

Carsten Kramer presented WP2, which focuses on novel detectors and components for future radio astronomy receivers. The total budget for WP2 is €1.8 million. Key industrial partners involved are:

- TTI Norte: Collaborating with ABUS in Spain on low-noise amplifiers.
- Lytid: Working with the Observatoire de Paris on local oscillators.
- DIRAMICS: Collaborating with OAN on the design of MMICs.

In addition, HES-SO has extensive contacts with industry to build micro-mechanical parts of tunable filters.

Kramer noted that the preparatory design phase is primarily conducted by academic institutions, with industrial partners becoming more involved in the follow-up work. He suggested that the IAB could help raise awareness of RADIOBLOCKS' activities among new industries and connect task coordinators with potential industry partners.

2.2.3 WP3: Digital Receivers

Stefan Heyminck presented WP3, which focuses on Phased Array Feeds, beamforming technologies and digital receivers. The work package includes activities such as algorithm development, hardware adaptation, and design studies. A key industry collaboration involves commercialising digital receivers via Hat Lab⁷, a spin-off company of INAF.

2.2.4 WP4: Data Transport and Correlation

John Romein introduced WP4, which centers on high-speed data transport and correlation. The work involves combining data from different receivers at a central location, typically using GPUs.

2.2.5 WP5: Data Processing Tool Kit

Marjolein Verkouter presented WP5, which focuses on developing an advanced data processing tool kit for radio astronomy. This work package has a broad scope and involves a large variety of activities. The main exploitation points are data compression, GPU programming, and high-performance computing.

⁷ <https://www.hat-lab.cloud/>

3 Key Outputs and Suggestions from the Advisory Board

The IAB suggested implementing a strategy to involve industrial partners as early as possible in the current or future projects. This could include creating a leaflet that clearly outlines the benefits for industry partners in engaging with EU-funded projects like RADIOBLOCKS. An action plan should involve hosting workshops with industry representatives to gather input on project design and objectives, publishing case studies on the project website and social media and presenting results at industry conferences and events.

3.1 Enhancing Industry Participation

The IAB emphasised the importance of showcasing the advantages for industries to participate in RADIOBLOCKS. This includes offering access to a comprehensive view of the entire signal chain and awareness of potential contact points.

The establishment of well-defined KPIs to measure the success of industry engagement was suggested. These KPIs could include the number of industry contacts made, the number of collaborative projects initiated, the number of technology licenses granted, and the overall impact on specific industries.

The IAB members also suggested exploring potential applications of RADIOBLOCKS technology in other fields such as telecommunications, aerospace, and defense.

3.2 Improving Communication and Dissemination

Industry standards and metrics should be adhered to in project communication, facilitating smoother adoption of RADIOBLOCKS results in industry.

The IAB advised presenting the project's applications and results prominently, with links to code and performance benchmarks, even if the results are still a work in progress. This approach will make it easier for potential industry partners to understand the practical value of RADIOBLOCKS technologies and will help attract potential collaborators earlier in the project lifecycle.

The IAB suggested participating in industry-focused conferences and events to disseminate project results and engage with potential industry partners. Specific events mentioned include commercial events such as Mobile World Congress, SciPy, and the GNU Radio Conferences.

3.3 Addressing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

A clear IP strategy should be defined that balances the principles of open science with the need to protect commercially valuable technologies. This strategy should define clear guidelines for IP ownership and licensing, providing a framework for managing IP in collaborative projects with industry partners by offering flexible licensing options. The use of more industry-friendly licenses, such as Apache 2.0 in open-source software with commercial applications, was suggested.

3.4 Actionable Steps and Future Meetings

Cimò summarised the discussion and outlined the next steps:

- A report of the meeting will be shared with the board members for comments and general feedback
- Communication and discussion with the board members should continue
- The possibility of an in-person meeting to facilitate more in-depth discussions will be explored.

This first meeting was considered constructive and useful. The intention is that, throughout the lifetime of the project, the IAB will continue to actively monitor and support RADIOBLOCKS.

4. Conclusions

The RADIOBLOCKS project has made excellent progress during its first period, as demonstrated by the very positive outcome of the first-year review. An important element of the project involves engaging with industry through the Industry Advisory Board (IAB). The IAB should provide guidance on both short- and long-term applications of project results within and beyond radio astronomy.

To further improve industrial participation and dissemination, the project should focus on developing a targeted value proposition that highlights the benefits for industry partners. These include access to cutting-edge technologies, opportunities for technological spin-offs, and close interactions with a network of leading research institutes. Early engagement strategies, such as workshops and advisory panels, can help involve industry partners during the initial stages of future projects.

Effective communication and dissemination strategies are crucial. The project should use industry-standard terminology, highlight practical applications and tangible results, and share work in progress to generate interest and attract collaborators. Participation in industry-specific events and enhancing the project's online presence can further improve dissemination efforts.

Addressing intellectual property rights is essential for balancing open science principles with commercial potential. A clear IP strategy, offering flexible licensing options, can accommodate the needs of different industry partners.

Overall, the RADIOBLOCKS project has the potential to drive innovation in radio astronomy and related fields. By actively engaging with industry, improving communication and dissemination strategies, and addressing intellectual property rights, the project can maximise its impact and ensure the long-term sustainability of its results.